

1 **Design of a NKG7 silencing regimen for treatment of treatment resistant very-early onset or early**
2 **onset IBD.**

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7 1. This document describes design of a NKG7 silencing regimen for treatment of treatment resistant
8 very-early onset or early onset IBD, or for induction of remission in emergency cases of severe IBD that
9 have failed other options.

10 2. The focus here is basic molecular description of the mechanisms underlying disease onset and
11 disease activity in humans with IBD.

12 3. The second major focus here is the putative involvement of natural killer cell function in this
13 process.

14 4. NKG7 is an immune receptor of the natural killer cell that is most classically understood to mark
15 activation of the natural killer cell.

16 5. We have recently defined a function for NKG7 in natural killer cells involving a second immune cell
17 type with potential importance to IBD discovery science, the gamma delta T cell.

18 6. The antibody targeting NKG7 (under development) is administered with a monoclonal antibody
19 targeting IL-23 p19, guselkumab, and a cyclosporine analog, tacrolimus.

20 7. The calcineurin inhibitor and cyclosporine analog targets refractory colitis while the IL23
21 neutralizing antibody targets steroid-resistant small bowel disease.

22 8. We are studying level clinical efficacy associated with immunoglobulin-assisted neutralization of
23 NKG7 to inhibit gut inflammatory natural killer cell activity.

24 9. Colectomy is not curative in patients with Crohn's Disease as it is in patients with Ulcerative
25 Colitis; the disease will return to the site of anastomosis.

26 10. Surgery has limited potential for IBD patients that have Crohn's Disease (options that are
27 sustainable).

28 11. Emergency treatment options for patients with severe IBD are required.

12. Patients with active, severe subtype B2 disease have limited opportunity for function-sparing
surgery in the small bowel to prevent restriction of feeding through stricture.

13. Quality of life associated with uncontrolled subtype B3 disease is poor and requires continual,
active management and emergency treatment options for GI providers.

14. An underlying hypothesis here is that NKG7 controls immune activation at the interface of the GI
tract and the immune system through a killer cell-mediated toleragenic function.

1 **Type 1 gamma delta T cells (Tyd) and type 17 Tyd can be distinguished based on expression of an**
2 **NK cell activation marker, NKG7.**

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7 Blood cells of the adaptive immune system can be identified as B or T lymphocytes. T lymphocytes are
8 characterized based on expression of the T-cell receptor as either alpha beta T cells or gamma delta T
9 cells. While alpha beta T cells engage in conventional antigen-specific responses by engaging
10 MHC:peptide complexes expressed on antigen presenting cells, gamma delta T cell defense is less well
11 understood but features recognition of non-classical ligands like lipid antigen expressed by CD1d and
12 interactions with MHC family receptors MR1 and MICA/MICB. Tyd cells are defined based on the nature
13 of their cytokine production as either type 1 or type 17 Tyd. We measured total transcription with next
14 generation sequencing to define the essential differences in Tyd1 and Tyd17. Tyd17 and Tyd1 were
15 defined by difference in expression of the natural killer cell activation marker, NKG7. We recently
16 demonstrated that NKG7 is functional in immunologic contexts involving loss of tolerogenic capacity, like in
17 stem cell transplant patients with graft versus host disease, and in solid organ transplant patients
18 experiencing acute rejection of the donor tissue. A second function we described for cells expressing
19 NKG7 was participating in tumor surveillance through engagement with killer cell surface receptor
20 KIR2DL3 and specific interactions of KIR2DL3 with class I MHC receptor HLA-V which marked cells
21 undergoing or having undergone transformation, which was further characterized by TCR receptor
22 switching from abTCR to ydTCR, indicating Tyd cells participated in tumor surveillance together with
23 natural killer cells. Together we concluded that a subset of Tyd cells can express the natural killer cell
24 activation marker NKG7, that the Tyd cells lineages Tyd1 and Tyd17 are defined by difference in
25 expression of NKG7, and that Tyd cell recruitment in tumor surveillance and homeostatic functions
26 requiring enforcement of tolerogenic signals at barriers and in transplant settings that feature natural killer
27 cell activation use a specific Tyd subset, Type I NKG7+ Tyd cells (Tyd1).
28

The type 3 innate lymphoid cell (ILC3) in humans with Crohn's Disease.

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A complete description of the sequence of events that results in development of the inflammatory bowel diseases Crohn's Disease and ulcerative colitis has not yet been defined. Hematopoietic derived cells of the gut that are relevant to IBD initiation and IBD biology include regulatory T cells, Th17 cells, lamina propria cells of the gut, intraepithelial IEC, and innate lymphoid cells (ILC) ILC1, ILC2 and ILC3. We provide here a brief description of the most distinguishing features of the ILC3 transcriptome in humans with Crohn's Disease. IBD-associated ILC3 purified based on CD45, CD127 and CD117 expression were CD2+, CD74+, CD38+, CD52+ and CD69+, CD59+ and CD48+. ILC3 displayed class II MHC receptors HLA-DRA, HLA-DPA1 and HLA-DMA but not MHC-I, expressed high levels of interferon stimulated genes including IFIT2, IFI44 and IFI6 as well as the inflammasome-associated guanylate binding proteins GBP3 and GBP5, expressed caspases CASP4 and CASP6 and the innate immune receptor PYCARD. ILC3 isolated from humans with Crohn's Disease expressed interleukins IL-18 and IL-15 and receptor subunits for the IL-11 and IL-13 cytokines. At the cell surface, inflammatory bowel disease-associated ILC3 were enriched for expression of TMEM128 and TMEM230 and TMEM9, GPR34 and GPR89A, and receptors AMIGO2, VSIG1 and PILRA. ILC3 from humans with Crohn's Disease rearranged or activated TCR delta constant region and joining genes while silencing or repressed TCR alpha and beta gene expression. Nuclear factor expression included THEMIS and IKZF3; the inflammatory bowel disease-associated ILC3 expressed grancalcin and the natural killer activation marker NKG7.

References

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Supporting Data

NKG7 functions in establishment of tolerance in the immune system.

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This study describes involvement of the activation marker NKG7 in multiple transplant biology settings and expression of the natural killer cell marker in the immune system. NKG7 expression marked the self non-self interface at the epithelial barrier in patients with sclerotic-type chronic graft versus host disease (GVHD). NKG7 was highly activated in the tissues in solid organs transplant patients: in heart during acute rejection following transplant and in bronchoalveolar lavage in lung transplant recipients undergoing acute rejection. In the immune system, we found enrichment of NKG7 in KIR2DL3+ cells. Together with recent description of KIR2DL3 as a cognate ligand for HLA-V, a class I MHC receptor that specifically marked transformed (cancerous) cells, the data described participation of activated natural killer cells in KIR2DL3:HLA-V dependant surveillance activity that also involves the gamma delta T cells (Tyd). We discovered functions for the natural killer cell marker NKG7 in tolerogenic functions associated with homeostatic self non-self discrimination that are disrupted in stem cell and solid organ transplant patients and in elimination of transformed cells associated with tumor surveillance.

Results

I. NKG7 expression marks the self non-self interface at the epithelial barrier in patients with sclerotic-type chronic graft versus host disease (GVHD)

II. In sclerotic skin tissue from autologous HSC transplant patients with chronic sclerotic type graft versus host disease, NKG7 is activated, along with T cell coreceptor CD2 the cluster of differentiation genes CD47, CD53, CD58, and CD59, chemokines including CCL3, CCL4, CCL5, CXCL8, CXCL9, cxcl10, CXCL11, and cxcl13, interferon pathway genes IFI44 and IFI27 and the interferon receptors IFNAR1 and IFNAR2, exhaustion receptors TIGIT and TIM-3 (HAVCR2), the programmed cell death molecule PDCD1LG2 and the TNF superfamily gene TNFSF4 that functions as a regulator of exhaustion (OX40L). Killer cell expression is activated including KLRD1, KLRG1 and KLRC4, as well as TIA, and cytotoxicity genes CD8a and GZMH. IL10 and IL15 were induced while IL11 was repressed.

III. NKG7 expression is evident during acute rejection in the heart

1 IV. NKG7 is co-expressed in natural killer cells together with a critical network of genes with immune
2 function.

3 Granzyme A

4 IFI27L1

5 PDCD10 and PDCD6

6 TNFSF4

7 CDK4 CDKN2C and CCNB1

8 CD59

9 IL24 and IL32

10 p53 target genes CDIP1 and PERP, as well as FAS

11 V. NKG7 expression is significantly higher in blood from humans with tolerance to a liver transplant
12 as compared to those with non tolerance (rejection)

13 In that context, it is co-expressed with CD2 and Cd47, as well as KLRD1

14 VI. NKG7 expression in lung transplant patients in bronchoalveolar lavage during acute rejection

15 Profile

16 GDS999 / 213915_at

17 Title

18 Bronchoalveolar lavage cells of lung transplant recipients with acute rejection

19 Organism

20 Homo sapiens

21 VII. NKG7 is expressed in natural killer cells upon activation and in cytotoxic T-cells, functions in
22 tolerance and likely influences T cell activation at the immunological synapse.

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VIII. NKG7 in the blood in patients with liver transplant.

Profile
GDS3282 / 213915_at
Title
Liver transplantation tolerance: peripheral blood mononuclear cells
Organism
Homo sapiens

IX. NKG7 is expressed in interferon producing dendritic killer cells

Profile
GDS1658 / 136058_at
Title
Dendritic cell subpopulations: spleen (MG-U74C)
Organism
Mus musculus

1 Basic immunology studies on NKG7.

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3 X. NKG7 is enriched in natural killer cells

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6 XI. NKG7 is an activation marker.

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8 XII. Expression of NKG7 in CD8 cytotoxic T cells alludes to a multicellular clearance mechanism
9 involving interactions between NKG7 expressing NK cells and and CD8+ T-cells

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11 XIII. Within the CD8 subset, NKG7 expression is associated with PD-L1 expression, implicating the
12 exhaustion program in enforcement of tolerance

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Other information on NKG7 in cellular and immune function in humans.

XIV. A spectrum of NKG7 expression in the hematopoietic system

XV. Survey of humans with melanoma did not reveal any gross changes in NKG7 during malignancy.